

Selection report **AQUARIUS TA** **Call I and II**

Alfred Wegener Institute

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1. Introduction

AQUARIUS will provide a highly comprehensive suite of integrated research infrastructures appropriate to addressing significant challenges for the long-term sustainability of our unique oceans, seas and freshwater ecosystems. An impressive range of 57 research infrastructure services will be made available to include research vessels, mobile marine observation platforms, aircraft, drones, satellite, sensors, fixed freshwater and marine observatories and test sites, experimental facilities, and sophisticated data infrastructures.

Through Transnational Access (TA) funding calls, the project will facilitate access to these research infrastructures, fostering large-scale, multidisciplinary projects aimed at generating impactful results.

The AQUARIUS Work Package (WP) 3 is devoted to the Transnational Access Call Design, Management, Evaluation and the TA Access Platform within AQUARIUS. The tasks in this WP include the preparation and management of a user-friendly TA management, application and evaluation platform, the launch of the TA calls, the handling of the scientific and logistical review process, and the post-access project evaluation.

The following TA calls were designed for AQUARIUS in [deliverable 3.3](#):

- 1) **Call 1 – Regional Lighthouse Access Call**. This call is looking for applications that address scientific challenges in the EU Lighthouse regions.
- 2) **Call 2 – Super-integrated Lighthouse Call**. This call will be responsive and shaped by the outcomes of the first call.

The scheduled dates of the AQUARIUS TA calls are the following:

- 1) Call 1: open **11 November 2024 – 20 January 2025**
- 2) Call 2: open **2 September 2025 – 28 October 2025**

The TA calls in AQUARIUS prioritise projects that align with the core objectives of Mission Ocean, ensuring a strong thematic and geographic focus on key regions such as the Baltic, North Sea, Black Sea, Atlantic/Arctic, and Mediterranean, along with their associated river systems.

This deliverable is dedicated to the evaluation and selection of the proposals submitted to the TA Call 1 – “Regional Lighthouse Access Call”. In this first AQUARIUS TA Call, AQUARIUS offered access to all infrastructures listed in the [AQUARIUS Infrastructure Catalogue](#).

1.1 Available infrastructures

The research infrastructures (RIs) that were offered in the first AQUARIUS TA call are categorised in the following nine categories:

- 1) Research Vessels
- 2) Marine Mobile Observation Platforms
- 3) Fixed Marine Facilities
- 4) Experimental Research Facilities
- 5) River & Basin Supersites

- 6) Aircraft
- 7) Drones
- 8) Satellite Services
- 9) Data Centers & Virtual Labs

2. The AQUARIUS evaluation system and process

The AQUARIUS proposal evaluation system is based on evaluation structures, procedures and best practices from previous Transnational Access projects (e.g. EUROFLEETS 1, 2 & Plus; ARICE; INTERACCESS; JERICO, JERICO-NEXT, JERICO-S3 and ASSEMBLE Plus).

Proposals submitted to the AQUARIUS calls are evaluated both scientifically and logistically:

1. **Scientific Evaluation:** Proposals are first evaluated scientifically by at least two scientific experts (referees). The evaluations are overseen by a Scientific Expert Panel (SEP), which ensures that the process is open, transparent, merit-based, impartial, and fair, strictly following the principles of equal opportunity. The panel also considers the alignment of the application with call topics and infrastructure integration. A consensus is reached by the Scientific Expert Panel as the final decision-making body.
2. **Logistical Feasibility Evaluation:** After the final recommendation of the Scientific Expert Panel, high-ranked proposals are examined by the AQUARIUS Operational Expert Panel (OEP) to determine the logistical feasibility of the proposed work. The decisions are finalized by the infrastructure operators, based on the recommendations from both the Scientific and Operational Expert Panels.

This evaluation process ensures that only scientifically excellent proposals are considered for funding. The selection of user groups is based on scientific excellence, and only those proposals that are highly ranked scientifically are considered for logistical evaluation and funding.

2.1 The evaluation workflow

Figure 1 provides an overview of the AQUARIUS Transnational Access call evaluation process. An overview of the process is provided below.

Figure 1: Work flow and different steps involved in the AQUARIUS evaluation procedure.

The incoming proposals received by the specified submission date are checked for compliance with the eligibility criteria by the Call Management Office (CMO). If proposals fail to meet the eligibility criteria they are excluded from the further evaluation process. Afterwards, the proposal is preliminary reviewed by the Operational Expert Panel (OEP) to check whether the logistical framework for the TA is fulfilled. In the following, the proposals are scientifically evaluated by members of the Scientific Evaluation Panel (SEP) and external, independent scientific experts. The SEP is established by the AQUARIUS Consortium and consists of international experts covering all fields of aquatic science.

Following this, a so called "guardian", i.e. a member of the SEP, who is an expert on the respective proposal topic, is allocated to each proposal by the chairs of the SEP and the CMO. The idea behind this concept is that the "guardian" accompanies the proposals he/she is responsible for throughout the different steps of the evaluation process and if the proposal is successful, even afterwards for reporting. The first task of a "guardian" in this respect is to recommend and suggest suitable reviewers for the individual assessment of proposals. In principle the review is carried out by a minimum of two individual experts for each proposal. With regard to this task the "guardian" is supported by the CMO which contacts the suggested reviewers and surveys the preparation and reception of individual assessments.

Each application is assessed by the scientific experts according to several evaluation criteria: Each criterion is scored from 1-5, where 1=weak, 2=satisfactory, 3=average, 4=good, 5=excellent, using a half-point score. The individual assessment criteria are weighted differently, with the scientific and technical quality of the planned research being the most important. The ranking of the applications is based on the total number of points that the applications have received for the criteria.

After the individual evaluation, the SEP meets for a consensus evaluation and draws up a ranking list of proposals and a shortlist of user groups recommended for funding.

After the final recommendation of the Scientific Expert Panel, high ranked proposals will be examined by the AQUARIUS Operational Expert Panel (OEP) to determine the logistical feasibility of the proposed work. The decisions are finalised by the infrastructure operators, based on the recommendations from the SEP and OEP.

2.2 AQUARIUS Scientific Expert Panel

The AQUARIUS Scientific Expert Panel (SEP) consists of international experts in the field, at least half of them independent from the consortium. Their expertise covers the main scientific disciplines and geographical areas offered within AQUARIUS.

Table 1: Members of the AQUARIUS Scientific Expert Panel

Name	First Name	Affiliation	Geographical area	Scientific Background
Martins	Inês	Instituto Hidrográfico	Atlantic	Marine Environment Monitoring
Tanhua	Toste	GEOMAR Helmholtz-Zentrum für Ozeanforschung Kiel	Atlantic	Ocean Chemistry
Casini	Michele	University of Bologna,	Atlantic	Aquatic Sciences
Reverdin	Gilles	CNRS	Atlantic	Ocean Circulation
Allcock	Louise	University of Galway	Atlantic	Marine Ecosystems
Bento	Ana Margarida	CIIMAR	Atlantic	Hazards Management
Nejstgaard	Jens Christian	Leibniz-Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB)	Atlantic	Aquatic Sciences
Ferradosa	Tiago	University of Porto	Atlantic	Ocean Waves
Forwick	Matthias	UiT The Arctic University of Norway,	North-Atlantic/Arctic	Bathymetry/Seafloor Topography
Barnes	David	British Antarctic Survey, UKRI	North-Atlantic/Arctic	Cryosphere
Lips	Urmas	Tallinn University of Technology	North-Atlantic/Arctic	Ocean Circulation
Nande	Manuel	CIIMAR	Atlantic	Aquatic Sciences
Carolyn	Faithfull	Swedish University of	Baltic Sea	Aquatic Sciences

		Agricultural Sciences		
Koehler	Birgit	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Aquatic Resources	Baltic Sea	Aquatic Sciences
Holmgren	Noel	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	Baltic Sea	Aquatic Ecosystems
Belgrano	Andrea	Institute of Marine Research	Baltic Sea	Aquatic Sciences
Boicenco	Laura	National Institute for Marine Research and Development "Grigore Antipa" (NIMRD)	Black Sea	Marine Ecosystems
Constantinescu	Adriana Maria	GeoEcoMar	Black Sea	Coastal Processes
Muresan	Mihaela	GeoEcoMar	Black Sea	Marine Ecosystems
Begun	Tatiana	GeoEcoMar	Black Sea	Marine Ecosystems
DUTU	Laura	GeoEcoMar	River systems	Freshwater Ecosystems
Guimarães	Laura	CIIMAR	River systems, e.g. Danube, Elbe, Ebro, Burrishoole Catchment	Aquatic Sciences
Menezes Pinheiro	Luis	University of Aveiro, Portugal	Atlantic	Marine Geophysics
Papetti	Chiara	University of Padova	Atlantic	Marine Ecosystems
Schroeder	Katrin	CNR-ISMAR	Mediterranean	Salinity/Density
Busetti	Martina	National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics	Mediterranean	Marine Geophysics
Morigi	Caterina	University of Pisa	North-Atlantic/Arctic	Paleoclimate Indicators
Mazzoldi	Carlotta	University of Padova	Mediterranean	Marine Ecosystems

3. First AQUARIUS Transnational Access Call: Regional Lighthouse Access Call

Proposals were submitted through the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Platform (TAP), a customised, user-friendly, online platform for AQUARIUS’ TA applications. The platform was customised especially for AQUARIUS, also based on the proposal submission needs of the Eurofleets projects (e.g. Eurofleets+ Grant Agreement No 824077).

In the TAP, applicants were asked to provide basic project details, the members of the user group and their contact information, the requested infrastructure and access units. In addition, the applications had to be supplemented with a research plan, a CV of the user group leader, an initial data management plan and, if applicable, a letter of recommendation.

3.1 Submitted applications to the Regional Lighthouse Access Call

Eighteen proposals were submitted as part of the first AQUARIUS Transnational Access Call. Following an eligibility check by the Call Management Office (WP3 lead, AWI), seventeen were found to be eligible for further scientific and logistic assessment according to the AQUARIUS evaluation workflow.

The reason for the ineligibility of one of the proposals was that it did not fulfil the eligibility criterion: “The proposals for the AQUARIUS TA calls must involve at least three partners from three different countries.”

The 17 eligible proposals applied for research topics and regions in the following EU Mission Lighthouse areas, as shown in Table 2:

Table 2: Requested EU Lighthouse Regions

Lighthouse region	No. of eligible applications
Arctic-Atlantic	10
Mediterranean Sea	4
Black Sea & River Danube	2
Baltic & North Sea	1

From the 65 infrastructures offered in the AQUARIUS RI catalogue, the following infrastructure types were requested:

- 13 Research Vessels
- 9 Mobile Marine Observation Platforms
- 3 Aircraft
- 2 Drones
- 2 Experimental Research Facilities
- 2 Fixed Marine Facilities
- 1 River and Basin Supersite

The most requested infrastructure was RV Celtic Explorer with six applications, related to two applications for UL_MRE-ROV 2 and two for AUV Barabas. Two proposals aimed to integrate five infrastructures, each.

Figure 2 shows the research infrastructures (RIs) requested in the AQUARIUS Regional Lighthouse Access Call.

Figure 2: Requested first-choice infrastructures of 1st AQUARIUS Transnational Access call. Y-Axis showing the number of proposals requesting the respective infrastructure.

The user group leaders were from 10 different countries: United Kingdom (5), Belgium (3), Cyprus (1), Germany (1), Denmark (1), Greenland (1), Italy, (2), The Netherlands (1), Poland (1), Romania (1).

Overall, applicants were based in 27 different countries (Figure 3), reflecting a high international collaboration. Most of the applicants were from Italy (20%), followed by the United Kingdom (12%), Belgium (11%), Denmark (8%) and Germany (6%).

Figure 3: Pie chart with the countries of current affiliations of the applicants in the first AQUARIUS Transnational Access call.

3.1.1. Status of the applicants

Three of the 18 proposals were submitted by early career PIs. Four of the applying user group leaders were women, 14 men. In total, the user groups had 86 (44%) female participants and 109 (56%) male participants, and one non-binary participant.

3.2 Scientific Evaluation

3.2.1 Logistic Pre-Check

Following the eligibility assessment, an initial logistical feasibility assessment was conducted by the OEP (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/evaluation-and-selection-procedure/#expertpanels>) to check whether the logistical framework for Transnational Access under AQUARIUS was met. OEP members from all EU Mission Ocean Regions participated in the meeting and assessed the logistical feasibility of the eligible proposals. All TA proposals were reviewed by the OEP in terms of deployment area, infrastructure availability and capability, required permits and authorisations, seasonal conditions during the proposed access, safety and risk issues, appropriate budget and costing. All eligible proposals were deemed realistic and realisable, even against the background of the very different infrastructures requested in the applications.

3.2.2 Scientific Evaluation

Following the eligibility check and a preliminary, logistical pre-check in January 2025, each proposal was assigned a Guardian within the Scientific Expert Panel. The scientific evaluators for the proposals were then chosen in mutual agreement by the SEP and the

CMO. Subsequently, each proposal was sent to external evaluators with the aim of obtaining at least two evaluations per proposal.

A total of 218 external evaluators were contacted for the evaluation process. 59 experts agreed to evaluate the 17 eligible proposals. The experts assessed the application(s) assigned to them using a dedicated **assessment form** in the AQUARIUS TAP. In the assessment form, the evaluators awarded marks on a rating scale for each of the AQUARIUS evaluation criteria. The ranking of the applications in the Consensus Evaluation was based on the total number of points that the applications have received for the criteria.

52 of the evaluators submitted the review in the TAP by the evaluation deadline in March 2025. The proposals received the minimum of 2 reviewers per proposal, and the majority of proposals also received 3 to 5 reviews.

3.2.3 SEP Consensus Evaluation Meeting

For the Regional Lighthouse Access Call, two SEP Consensus Evaluation meetings were organised. Both meetings took place online. The first meeting took place on 21 March 2025. During this meeting, the proposals submitted for the Mediterranean Sea, North and Baltic Sea, and Black Sea and River Systems were discussed. The second consensus meeting was scheduled for March 27th, 2025. During this meeting, the proposals for the Arctic-Atlantic region were discussed. The meeting was concluded with a discussion on the ranking of all proposals submitted to the first TA call.

The discussions during the meetings were based on presentations of the proposal guardians, summarising the outcomes of the scientific evaluation per proposal. The external, scientific evaluations, as well as the comments and judgements made during the SEP discussion was used to prepare a consensus evaluation statement as feedback to the applicants. The statement/feedback does not contain any evaluation scores, but general recommendations whether to fund or not a proposal, as well as recommendations for improvement.

The actual evaluation of proposals was carried out as follows. All proposals were discussed and evaluated according to the AQUARIUS TA Call evaluation criteria (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/evaluation-and-selection-procedure/>).

Primary criteria were the scientific quality of the planned research and of the work programme, as well as the scientific impact and the scientific competence of the user-group. Further secondary criteria, like collaborative applications from teams and institutions where no equivalent research infrastructure exist, collaboration with vulnerable groups such as researchers from Ukraine and researchers with refugee status, and the inclusion of female, young and early career scientists or citizen science groups, were also considered.

The guardian gave a report and commented on the received reviews for a given proposal followed by an open discussion. Each of the proposals was assigned to the following categories defined previously in the "Guidelines for Applicants":

- A - Recommended for scheduling
- B – On hold

- C - Not recommended for scheduling

Based on the evaluation score, discussion and agreement of the SEP, all proposals recommended for scheduling ("A") were ranked as 1st choice (A1), 2nd choice (A2), ... for implementation.

3.2.4 Outcome of the scientific evaluation

The SEP recommended the following during the consensus evaluation meetings, held online on 21 and 27 March 2025: 11 proposals were proposed for scheduling with highest (A1) priority, 3 were ranked in category B, and 3 were not recommended for funding (C) (Table 3). The proposals in category C were not considered for the logistic evaluation. See Table 3 for details.

3.3 Outcome of the logistic evaluation

After the final recommendation by the SEP, the proposals were recommended for scheduling within the AQUARIUS TAP workflow for further logistical evaluation or not. Consequently, RI managers could confirm the requested access to their RI or propose changes in terms of access units, access time or budget. Subsequently, the proposals were thoroughly reviewed by the AQUARIUS Operational Expert Panel (OEP) to determine the logistical feasibility and timing of the proposed work. 14 proposals were reviewed, and all were deemed operationally feasible based on the infrastructure(s) requested and the achievable objectives within the research plan.

Proposal 26, aiming to integrate 3 infrastructures required a meeting to determine the interoperability of a research vessel and 2 marine mobile observation platforms. This was held online with the respective infrastructure operators who were confident about achieving the proposal's aims. However, all agreed that an additional two days of access were required for mobilising and integrating the mobile platforms on board the research vessel.

The logistical evaluation of proposal 18 identified the need to change the demobilisation port from Nuuk to Iceland (most likely Reykjavik) in order to comply with the vessel's schedule. The change was flagged with the applicant, who requested an additional 2 days of access be granted, as the change of port would mean having to drop a component of their proposed work plan. The increase was agreed with the vessel operator and 22 days were granted in total.

The logistical evaluation of proposal 11 involved an interoperability meeting between the research vessel operator and ROV operator. In order to save on ROV transport costs and for the efficient use of time and resources, it was agreed to mobilise the ROV onto the vessel while the vessel was in the home port preparing for the preceding survey. The ROV would then remain onboard the vessel during this survey. The logistical evaluation also deemed it necessary to demobilise in the home port rather than near the work area (Iceland) to simplify the demobilisation and transport logistics of the ROV and associated launch and recovery systems. This change of demobilisation port resulted in an increase in the number of granted units of access by 3 days to account for the transit to the demob port during which time the ROV demobilisation can begin and acquired data processed.

Proposal 29 faced some logistical challenges in scheduling the requested first choice vessel, primarily due to the remote location of the work proposed. The 2nd option vessel was also considered but faced similar logistical issues due to the distance between the work area and the vessel’s home port, and the transit time required to travel to the remote work area. Logistical evaluations for this proposal are still ongoing and awaiting confirmation from the first-choice vessel regarding their national program schedule. Other research vessels in the AQUARIUS catalogue are also being contacted to determine availability and feasibility.

Scheduling Proposal 17 on the requested vessel presents logistical challenges also, as the applicant’s preferred timeframe conflicts with the vessel’s annual national commitments and limited availability as a result. As such, logistical evaluations for this proposal are still ongoing, and other vessels are begin contacted as alternative options.

Five other proposals, requesting only one research infrastructure each were all reviewed by the respective infrastructure operators and were all deemed logistically feasible.

One proposal (ID 8) will not be funded via AQUARIUS as the applicant had submitted the same funding proposal via POLARIN: Polar Research Infrastructure Network project (Grant ID 101130949) which was successful and will therefore be funded by this project.

Table 3: Proposals recommended for scheduling by the SEP.

PROPOSAL ID	REQUESTED RI(S)	2ND OPTION RI	OVERALL RANKING	OEP DECISION
26	RV G. O. Sars, AUV Barabas, Glider Yoko	RV Celtic Explorer, AUV Barabas, Glider Yoko	A1	Granted
29	RV Celtic Explorer	RV Sarmiento de Gamboa	A2	TBC
16	Utö Marine and Atmospheric Research Station	RV Aranda	A3	Granted
8	RV Celtic Explorer	RV G. O. Sars	A4	Not granted as access provided through POLARIN
22	SOCIB Glider Facility		A5	Granted
30	RV Arni Fridriksson	RV G. O. Sars	A6	Granted
18	RV Celtic Explorer		A7	Granted
11	UL_MRE-ROV, RV Celtic Explorer	RV G. O. Sars	A8	Granted
19	RV Tubitak Marmara		A9	Granted
21	RV Mare Nigrum	RV Tubitak Marmara	A10	Granted

17	RV Jákup Sverri	RV Celtic Explorer	A11	TBC
27	UL_MRE-ROV, RV Celtic Explorer, AUV Barabas		B1	On hold
7	UL Inspection ROV, RV Thalassa		B2	On hold
23	RV Aegaeo, Max Rover, South Adriatic Sea E2M3A EMSO Regional Facility, EMBRC-SBR, EMBRC-OOB	RV Thalassa	B3	On hold
14	RV Celtic Explorer		C	Not recommended for scheduling
32	UL Drone, FLIS, AIRS, CWIS-II (AVIRIS-4), MAPEO		C	Not recommended for scheduling
20	iCIEM Ebro Delta Supersite		C	Not recommended for scheduling

Following communication with each of the Research Infrastructure operators to confirm availability of the infrastructures and suitability for use of equipment, 10 highly ranked research projects, representing an AQUARIUS Regional Lighthouse Call success rate of 59%, will receive access to 298 units fully funded by the AQUARIUS project (see Table 4). Pending the logistic evaluation of the two remaining proposals, this figure could reach as high as 333 units of daily access.

Table 4: Proposals with access scheduled after the logistic evaluation.

REQUESTED RI(s)	PROJECT NAME	SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINE	AREA	FUNDED ACCESS UNITS
RV G. O. Sars, AUV Barabas, Glider Yoko	DENGATE	Global change & Climate observation	Atlantic -Arctic	RV G. O. Sars (14 days), AUV Barabas (16 days), Glider Yoko (16 days), 46 Days Total
RV Celtic Explorer	Rock-IT	Natural Hazards	Atlantic -Arctic	TBC
Utö Marine and Atmospheric Research Station	BASEVOC	Oceanography	Baltic Sea	100 Days Total
RV Celtic Explorer	BlueCFjords	Earth Sciences	Atlantic -Arctic	POLARIN Funded
SOCIB Glider Facility	ABACUS 2026	Oceanography	Mediterranean Sea	54 Days Total
RV Arni Fridriksson	E(ddies)GC	Oceanography	Atlantic -Arctic	10 Days Total

RV Celtic Explorer	AR7E-2026	Oceanography	Atlantic -Arctic	22 Days Total
UL_MRE-ROV, RV Celtic Explorer	GREAT	Ecosystems and Biodiversity	Atlantic -Arctic	UL_MRE-ROV (19 Days) RV Celtic Explorer (19 Days) 38 Days Total
RV Tubitak Marmara	ASTRA	Oceanography	Black Sea	15 Days Total
RV Mare Nigrum	STREAM-DANUBE	Oceanography	Danube River	13 Days Total
RV Jákup Sverri	CRUST	Oceanography	Atlantic -Arctic	TBC

Three proposals (27, 7, and 23) were placed 'On Hold' (see Table 3). The vessel operator involved in proposal 7 deemed the chosen vessel unsuitable for the planned work, and after communications with the PI it was decided that the proposal was not logistically feasible. The PI was encouraged to review their application and resubmit in the second AQUARIUS Call. Proposals 23 and 27 remain on hold and pending the final logistic evaluations of Call 1 proposals, may be scheduled.

Both expert panels accomplished their respective tasks. The partition into two steps, with a scientific evaluation of proposals before taking into account any logistical considerations, guarantees that only excellent proposals are awarded units of access through AQUARIUS.

3.4 Outlook: Second TA Call

The second TA call, the "AQUARIUS Funding Call - Marine and Freshwater Infrastructure Access", will open on September 2, 2025, and will close on October 28, 2025.

The second AQUARIUS TA call is designed to be responsive and shaped by the outcomes of the first call. It will focus more on the key challenges identified for Call 1 that affect more than one of the EU Mission Ocean and Waters regions. This approach will ensure that the second call is even more flexible than call 1 in terms of cross-cutting topics and regions and can respond to the evolving needs and priorities of the research community and stakeholders.

The infrastructures that will be available in the second TA call will be listed at <https://aquarius-ri.eu/access/> and in the Transnational Access Platform.